

hydroxide. In the present investigation an absorption at 315-385 cm^{-1} in the spectra of adducts has been assigned to this mode of vibration, which unequivocally supports the oxygen atom being the donating centre in various heterocyclic amine *N*-oxide. Two Sn-O stretching mode of vibration at 345 and 315 cm^{-1} in the adduct $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot \text{DipyO}_2$ support bidentate character of the ligand.

The bands at ~ 255 and 265 cm^{-1} of weak intensity, observed in tin(II) isothiocyanate were assigned to Sn←N stretching vibration and is consistent with the presence at two crystallographically distinct N-bonded thiocyanate groups as shown recently by X-ray diffraction. The corresponding bands in the adducts are observed at ~ 270 and 260 cm^{-1} , which is lower than reported earlier by Nakamoto¹⁷ and Bhide¹⁸ in some tin(II) complexes containing Sn-N bond. A slight decrease in $\nu_{\text{Sn-N}}$ may be due to the lower oxidation state and higher coordination number of the tin metal.

The Sn-Cl stretching vibration has been identified at about 280 cm^{-1} , which is in agreement with earlier reports on tin(II) chloride adducts⁸. The Sn-Br stretching vibration could not be identified in the present investigation as it lies beyond the recorded range of the vibration.

Thus, on the basis of foregoing discussion and analogy with the previous work, the molecular adducts $\text{SnX}_2 \cdot \text{L}$ (where X=Br or NCS, and L=2-PicO, 3-PicO, 4-PicO, LutO, QO and IsqO), in which tin is three-coordinated, may have pyramidal structure due to sp^3 hybridization in which one of the sites is occupied by a stereochemically active lone pair. The adducts $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$, [where L=QO or IsqO] and $\text{SnX}_2 \cdot \text{L}$ (where X=Cl, Br or NCS, and L=a bidentate ligand, DipyO_2), in which tin is four-coordinated may have trigonal bipyramidal structure, with stereochemically active lone pair occupying one of the sites.

Acknowledgement

The authors are earnestly thankful to Sri J. N. Srivastava, Head, Chemistry Department, B.S.N.V. and Degree College, Lucknow for providing facilities, to Dr. D. P. Bajpai, Principal, B.S.N.V. Degree College, Lucknow for his encouragement. We are also indebted to C.D.R.I., Lucknow for microanalysis and recording ir spectra.

References

1. J. D. DONALDSON, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **8**, 287.
2. J. S. MORRISON and H. M. HAENDLER, *J. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 393.
3. J. K. LEEB and P. A. FLINN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 882.
4. V. I. GOLDANSKII, V. V. KHRAPOV, V. Y. ROZHEV, T. N. TUMAROKOVA and D. E. SURPINA, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1968, **183**, 864.
5. J. D. DONALDSON and D. G. NICHOLSON, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1970, 146.
6. E. HOUGH and D. G. NICHOLSON, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 1782.
7. J. W. KAUFFMAN, D. H. MOOR and B. J. WILLIAMS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1165.
8. K. D. CHUGR, P. UMAPATHY and D. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 864.
9. T. B. ABSI, R. S. MAKHIJA and M. ONYSZCHUK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 2039.
10. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and B. K. DWIVEDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 599.
11. B. R. CHAMBERLAIN and W. MOSER, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1969, 854.
12. E. OOHAI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 534.
13. M. ROBINSON and B. ROBINSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 1337.
14. *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1955, **75**, 731.
15. C. G. DAVIES and J. D. DONALDSON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 2635.
16. W. D. HONRICK and J. J. ZUCKERMAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 3034.
17. D. TEVAULT and K. NAKAMOTO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 1282.
18. S. N. BHIDE, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 861.

Transition Metal Schiff Base Chelates as Ligands towards Tin(II) Halides and -Isothiocyanate

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Manuscript received 21 March 1984, revised 16 October 1984,
accepted 15 February 1986

THE transition metal-Schiff base chelates derived from tetradentate or bidentate Schiff bases have been extensively studied as ligands towards transition and non-transition metal ions and have been reviewed^{1,2}. Among the group IVB metals tin(IV) and tin(II) halides³ are reported to yield neutral 1:1 adducts with *N,N'*-ethylenebis(salicylideneimino)metal(II) M Salen, M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, which have been shown to coordinate through phenolic O atoms. It has also been shown that Co^{II}(Salen)SnX₂ undergoes halide exchange in polar solvents, but exchange does not occur in the Co^{II}(Salen)SnX₂ adduct. However, studies using transition metal Schiff base complexes as ligands towards tin(II) acceptors are scarce.

In the present investigation several tin(II) isothiocyanate adducts of M Salen have been synthesised and characterised. Recently Srivastava *et al.*⁴ have also reported the synthesis and characterisation of binuclear adducts of organotin(IV) chlorides with the metal chelates of tetradentate Schiff bases derived from ketones such as acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone. It was considered of interest to study further the coordinative interaction of tin(II) halides and isothiocyanate with complex metal chelate ligands

NOTES

derived from ketones. The present paper describes the interaction of the following transition metal Schiff base complexes (Table 1) as ligands towards tin(II) acceptors.

TABLE 1—SPECIFICATION OF M, R AND R' IN LIGAND

Structure	M(II)	R	R'	Abbreviation
1	Ni	-CH ₃ ; OH ₂ -	H	NiL-1
1	Cu	-CH ₃ ; OH ₂ -	H	CuL-1
1	Ni	-CH ₃ ; OH ₂ -	Me	NiL-2
1	Cu	-CH ₃ ; OH ₂ -	Me	CuL-2
2	Ni	-OH ₂ ; OH ₂ -	—	NiL-3
2	Cu	-OH ₂ ; OH ₂ -	—	CuL-3
2	Ni	-OH ₂ ; -OHMe-	—	NiL-4
2	Cu	-OH ₂ ; -OHMe-	—	CuL-4

Experimental

All the aldehyde, ketones and diamines used in the synthesis of Schiff bases were reagent grade. The Schiff bases and their complexes with nickel(II), and copper(II) were prepared by the reported methods^{5,6} and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous calcium chloride before use. Dihydrated stannous chloride (S. Merck) was used as such. Tin(II) bromide was prepared as a pale yellow crystalline

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR SnX₂.ML COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν _{C-O} [*] cm ⁻¹ Adduct
			Sn	Ni/Cu	X	
Sn(NCS) ₂ .NiL-1	Orange	175d	21.28 (21.20)	10.51 (10.48)	—	1545s (1540s)
Sn(NCS) ₂ .CuL-1	Yellow	180d	21.21 (21.02)	11.18 (11.26)	—	1550s (1540s, 1530s)
SnCl ₂ .NiL-2	Light yellow	>240	23.12 (23.07)	11.85 (11.41)	13.65 (13.77)	1545s (1530vs)
SnBr ₂ .NiL-2	Yellow	>240	19.70 (19.65)	9.87 (9.72)	26.61 (26.45)	1550s
Sn(NCS) ₂ .NiL-2	Dirty orange	>240	21.18 (21.20)	10.35 (10.48)	—	1545s
SnCl ₂ .CuL-2	Dull yellow	>240	22.98 (22.86)	12.82 (12.24)	13.75 (13.65)	1545s (1528vs)
SnBr ₂ .CuL-2	Dull yellow	>240	19.61 (19.52)	10.51 (10.45)	26.18 (26.27)	1544s
Sn(NCS) ₂ .CuL-2	Light yellow	>240	21.11 (21.02)	11.05 (11.26)	—	1550m
SnCl ₂ .NiL-3	Light brown	280d	25.03 (25.23)	12.85 (12.47)	15.01 (15.07)	1125w (1220w)
SnBr ₂ .NiL-3	Brown	220d	21.12 (21.22)	9.98 (10.50)	28.46 (28.57)	1125w
Sn(NCS) ₂ .NiL-3	Dull white	176d	22.98 (23.01)	11.07 (11.88)	—	1140m
SnCl ₂ .CuL-3	Light green	170d	25.00 (24.97)	12.60 (12.37)	14.85 (14.90)	1120w (1110m)
SnBr ₂ .CuL-3	Greenish yellow	205d	21.16 (21.04)	11.86 (11.27)	28.01 (28.32)	1120w
Sn(NCS) ₂ .CuL-3	Dull white	171d	23.12 (22.80)	12.04 (12.20)	—	1130m
SnCl ₂ .NiL-4	Light green	270d	25.12 (24.50)	11.99 (12.12)	14.26 (14.63)	1140s (1140s)
SnBr ₂ .NiL-4	Brown	218d	21.10 (20.69)	9.98 (10.23)	27.84 (27.86)	1145s
Sn(NCS) ₂ .NiL-4	Dull white	200d	22.08 (22.41)	10.95 (11.08)	—	1140m
SnCl ₂ .CuL-4	Light green	140d	24.12 (24.25)	12.58 (12.98)	14.32 (14.48)	1130m (1130s)
SnBr ₂ .CuL-4	Dirty yellow	180d	20.85 (20.53)	10.68 (10.99)	27.26 (27.64)	1130s
Sn(NCS) ₂ .CuL-4	Dull white	198d	22.82 (22.20)	11.59 (11.89)	—	1140w

* Metal-ligand complex in parentheses.

solid by dissolving powdered tin in hot hydrobromic acid and gently evaporating the solution. Anhydrous stannous chloride and stannous bromide were prepared by stirring the corresponding hydrated halide with acetic anhydride. The mixture was filtered, washed several times with cold dry petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo* at 200°. The tin(II) isothiocyanate was obtained by the published method⁷.

The binuclear adducts of tin(II) chloride, bromide and isothiocyanate were prepared by the direct interaction of Lewis acids in absolute ethanol and ligand in methylenedichloride. In a typical experiment, a solution of NiL-1 (0.01 mmol, 3.25 g) was dissolved in refluxing methylenedichloride under an atmosphere of dry nitrogen. The solution of $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ (0.01 mmol, 2.4 g) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) was slowly added to NiL-1 solution. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen atmosphere and the precipitated solid was filtered, washed with methylene dichloride and dried *in vacuo*. The solid adducts were found to be stable in air.

The binuclear complexes were analysed for tin, nickel, copper and chlorine by standard procedure⁸, the analytical data are given in Table 2. Molar conductance of complexes soluble in dimethylacetamide were measured at $10^{-3}M$ concentration with the help of a Phillips PR 950 conductivity bridge. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a T.G.A. apparatus supplied by Fertilizer Corporation of India. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in the 4000-500 cm^{-1} region.

Results and Discussion

All the newly synthesised molecular adducts are light green to dirty white solids, which decompose on heating except those of tin(II) isothiocyanate with M Salen which are orange. The analytical data corresponds to 1:1 (Sn^{II} : metal chelate) stoichiometry irrespective of the nature of the Schiff base and transition metal ion used.

A comparison of the electronic spectra of the free transition metal Schiff base chelate (NiL-1) with the corresponding adduct with tin(II) isothiocyanate, *i.e.* $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{NiL-1}$ in dimethylacetamide shows absorption at almost identical place, clearly indicating the dissociation of the binuclear complex in this solvent. The molar conductance data of $10^{-3}M$ solution of the adduct in dimethylacetamide are of the same order as those of the free tin(II) isothiocyanate in the same concentration range. This supports well the conclusion derived from uv spectral studies that the complex is largely dissociated into the parent components. The results agree well with the earlier observation on the corresponding adducts of phenyltin(IV) chlorides⁴ and tin(II) chlorides^{9,10} with Schiff bases.

Thermogravimetric analysis of a representative adduct namely $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{NiL-1}$ (Fig. 1) reveals the decomposition of the compound in two stages. The

weight loss steps occurring at 15.85 and 60.33% indicate the decomposition of $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{NiL-1}$ to Ni Salen and SnS_2 and then to NiO and SnO_2 , respectively. Theoretical weight loss are 15.04 and 59.74% for the first and second steps, respectively.

Fig. 1. Pyrolysis curve of $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{Ni}(\text{OOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$.

The non-volatile residue was 39.67% (theoretical 40.20%) which compares favourably with the value expected if a mixture of nickel and tin(IV) oxide is the final product.

Ir spectra: The infrared spectra of the transition metal Schiff base chelates have almost identical absorptions. The ir spectra of the adducts are also not very different from each other excepting typical absorption of the thiocyanate group.

The main evidence of adduct formation by the transition metal Schiff base complex with tin(II) is shown by an increase in the position of C-O stretching vibration. Two bands are observed for Cu^{II} Salen at 1540 and 1530 cm^{-1} , whereas only one is present in Ni^{II} Salen at 1540 cm^{-1} . On forming adducts with tin(II) isothiocyanate only one absorption is observed at slightly higher frequency indicating the formation of binuclear complex through bridging at the phenolic oxygen of the metal chelates. The conclusion is in accordance with the earlier observations for tin(II) halide adducts of these complex ligands⁸.

The positive shifting of this band in the adducts of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} chelates of Schiff bases derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenone is greater as compared to those derived from salicylaldehyde, *i.e.* Salen, which may be attributed to the electron repelling behaviour of the methyl group attached to one of the carbon atoms of the ring containing the transition metal.

The spectra of the transition metal chelates of tetradentate Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of acetylacetone and ethylenediamine or propylenediamide consist of a band at $\sim 1120\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which has unequivocally been assigned to the stretching vibration of C—O linkage in the metal chelate ring¹¹. When the complex ligand acts as Lewis bases towards tin(II) halides or isothiocyanate, the spectra of the resulting products show little change in the position of this absorption, thereby suggesting only a weak coordination of tin(II) with the diketo-imine transition metal complex ligands. The conclusion is supported by the reported observations that the triple coordination occurs more readily *via* phenolic oxygen rather than diketo-imine oxygen^{4,12,13}.

The $\nu_{\text{Sn-O}}$ occurs over an exceptionally wide range of frequency depending upon the nature of bonding between the two atoms. In the present investigation, the coordination of tin(II) moieties with the phenolic or alcoholic oxygen (metal diketoimine ring oxygen) is supported by the appearance of a band at $\sim 600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is absent in the spectra of the corresponding complex ligands. Similar assignment have been made in case of tin(II) chelates^{14,15} and organotin(IV) halide adducts with Salen¹⁶ and M Salen¹⁷. The Sn—Cl and Sn—Br stretching vibrations could not be identified since they lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

NCS absorption: In the present investigation the splitting of the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ absorptions in the ir of the solid adducts in the range of 2148-2000 and 860-800 cm^{-1} , respectively indicates the presence of two crystallographically distinct thiocyanate groups N-bonded to the metal atom. The results are in good agreement with reported data for tin(II) isothiocyanate^{7,18} and their adducts with some O-N-donor ligands¹⁹.

On the basis of the foregoing discussion it is evident that transition metal chelates of tetradentate bases derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone or acetylacetone and diamines form molecular adducts of 1:1 stoichiometry with tin(II) chloride, bromide and isothiocyanate. The newly synthesised coordination compounds contain two triply bonded oxygen atoms. The tin(II) halides behave primarily as monofunctional acceptor although empty d-orbitals are available for additional bonding. The following probable structure of the complexes involving four coordinated tin(II) atom in combination with the bidentate complex ligand could not be made with certainty owing to the

insolubility of the compounds in common organic solvents which restricted studies in solution and also due to the lack of facilities for X-ray analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors are most grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for granting Teachers' Fellowship to one of them (B.K.D.) and the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for recording ir spectra.

References

1. E. SINN and C. M. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, 4, 391.
2. I^r. MILBURN, M. R. TRUTER and B. L. VICKERY, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 841.
3. M. D. HODDAY and T. D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1971, 1453.
4. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, A. K. S. CHAUHAN and M. AGARWAL, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1978, 3, 878.
5. J. M. PAUL, J. H. RICHARD, K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 5820.
6. E. L. OLSZEWSKI and D. F. MARTIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1577.
7. B. R. CHAMBERLAIN and W. MÖSER, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1969, 854.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Richard Clay and Co., London, 1961.
9. G. C. STOCIO, G. ALONZO, N. BERTAZZI and F. D. BIANCA, *Gass. Chim. Ital.*, 1975, 105, 355.
10. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, A. K. S. CHAUHAN and B. K. DWIVEDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 269.
11. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 56, 998.
12. G. A. BARCLAY and B. P. HOSKINS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1979.
13. S. M. KUMAR and F. HENRY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, 41, 1682.
14. P. R. F. EWINGS and P. G. HARRISON, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 1717.
15. P. G. HARRISON and S. R. STOBART, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 940.
16. E. BARBIERI and R. H. HERBER, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1972, 42, 65.
17. L. PELLERITO, R. ORFALU, A. GIANGUZZA and R. BARBIERI, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1974, 70, 303.

Reaction of Lead Tetraacetate with Cholest-5-ene and Its 3 β -Substituted Derivatives

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Manuscript received 19 May 1983, revised 20 July 1984,
accepted 18 January 1985

MIHAILOVIC *et al.*¹ synthesised 7-acetoxyated derivative from the reaction of lead tetraacetate with 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene. But it has been